

Template of answers for assessing the respondent's understandings of diabetes

Participant no. _____

Gender: Male Female

Age: _____

Study/training: _____

On medication: Yes No

Details of the medication: _____

Assist other's medication: Yes No

Visited health facility: _____

Diabetes is:

- Body does not properly process food for use as energy.
- Body either doesn't make enough insulin or can't use its own insulin as well as it should.
- Sugars to build up in the blood.
- Diabetes can cause serious health complications.

Types of diabetes:

- Type 1
 - The pancreas stops producing insulin.
 - It usually starts in young people under the age of 30.
 - The onset is sudden and dramatic.
 - Must inject insulin to survive.
 - Balance with food intake and exercise programmes.

- Type 2
 - The insulin, which the pancreas produces, is either not enough or does not work properly.
 - Most type 2's are over 40.
 - Approximately 85 – 90% of all people with diabetes are type 2.
 - People who have this condition are undiagnosed.
 - May be treated successfully without medication. Tablets may be prescribed to help improve control, however, many type 2's will eventually use insulin.
 - Weight alone will reduce glucose levels. Eating patterns and exercise play important roles in management.

- Gestational A temporary condition that occurs during pregnancy. Both mother and child have an increased risk of developing diabetes in the future.
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- Symptoms or signs of diabetes:**
- Unusual thirst
 - Frequent urination
 - Unusual weight loss
 - Extreme fatigue or lack of energy
 - Blurred vision
 - Frequent or recurring infections
 - Cuts and bruises that are slow to heal, boils and itching skin
 - Tingling and numbness in the hands or feet
 - People with type 2 diabetes may show no symptoms
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Risk factors of diabetes:

- Being aged 35 or over
 - Being overweight (especially if you carry most of your weight around your middle).
 - Being a member of a high-risk group (in South Africa, if you are of Indian descent you are at particular risk).
 - Having a family history of diabetes
 - Having given birth to a baby that weighed over 4kg at birth, or have had gestational diabetes during pregnancy
 - Having high cholesterol or other fats in the blood
 - Having high blood pressure or heart disease
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- Reduce the risk of becoming diabetic:**
- Healthy diet
 - Weight control
 - Exercise
 - Reduction in stress
 - No smoking
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What to do if you suspect of having diabetes:

- Be tested every year
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- Health complications:**
- Blindness
 - High blood pressure
 - Heart attack
 - Stroke
 - Kidney failure
 - Impotence
 - Sexual dysfunction
 - Amputation

To improve health conditions and prevent complications: Healthy eating Exercise
 Medication Foot care Blood glucose testing

Information that would like to know when having diabetes:

How the doctor should explain about the diagnosed disease:

[Name: _____
Contact number: _____]